

EHTIMOLLAR NAZARIYASIDA HODISALAR YIG'INDISI VA KO'PAYTMASI SUM AND MULTIPLICATION OF EVENTS IN THE THEORY OF PROBABILITY

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Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda matematikaning differensial tenglamalar bo'limi juda rivojlanmoqda. Ta'lim sohasida esa alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Shu bilan birgalikda differensial tenglamalar orqali ko'pgina masalalar o'z yechimini topmoqda. Ushbu maqolada birinchi tartibli bir jinsli differensial tenglamalar haqida ma'lumot va bunday ko'rinishdagi tenglamalarni qanday ishlash bir nechta misol yordamida ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: differensial tenglamalar, bir jinsli differensial tenglamalar, uzluksiz funksiyalar, umumiy yechim, o'zgaruvchilari ajraladigan differensial tenglamalar, integral, birinchi tartibli bir jinsli differensial tenglamalar.

Annotation: Today, the branch of differential equations of mathematics is developing very much. Special attention is being paid in the field of education. At the same time, many problems are being solved through differential equations. This article provides information on first-order homogeneous differential equations and how to work with equations of this form using several examples.

Key words: differential equations, homogeneous differential equations. continuous functions, general solution, differential equations with separable variables, integral, homogeneous differential equations of the first order.

A va B yig'indisi $A+B$ deb, A hodisa yoki B hodisaning, yo bu ikkala hodisaning ham ro'y berishidan iborat hodisaga aytiladi.

Masalan, to'pdan ikkita snaryad otilgan bo'lib, A birinchi otishda nishonga tegish, B ikkinchi otishda nishonga tegish hodisalari bo'lsa, u holda $A+B$ birinchi otishda yoki ikkinchi yoki ikkala otishda ham nishonga tegish hodisasi bo'lladi.

Bir necha hodisalarning yig'indisi deb, bu hodisalardan kamida birining ro'y berishidan iborat bo'lgan hodisaga aytiladi.

Teorema. Birgalikda bo'lmagan ikkita hodisadan qaysi biri bo'lsa ham, bittasining ro'y berish ehtimoli shu hodisalar ehtimollarining yig'indisiga teng:

$$P(A + B) = P(A) + P(B)$$

Isboti. Quyidagicha belgilash kiritamiz:

n - sinashning mumkin bo'lgan elementar natijalari jami soni;

m_1 - A hodisaga qulaylik tug'diradigan natijalar soni;

m_2 - B hodisaga qulaylik tug'diradigan natijalar soni.

Yo A hodisa, yoki B hodisa ro‘y berishiga qulaylik tug‘diradigan natijalar soni m_1+m_2 ga teng. Demak,

$$P(A+B) = \frac{m_1+m_2}{n} = \frac{m_1}{n} + \frac{m_2}{n}.$$

$$\frac{m_1}{n} = P(A) \quad \text{va} \quad \frac{m_2}{n} = P(B)$$

ligini nazarda tutib, uzil- kesil

$$P(A+B) = P(A) + P(B)$$

munosabatni hosil qilamiz.

Natija. Har ikkalasi birgalikda bo‘lmagan bir nechta hodisalardan qaysinisi bo‘lsa ham, birining ro‘y berish ehtimoli shu hodisalar ehtimollari yig‘indisiga teng:

$$P(A_1 + A_2 + \dots + A_n) = P(A_1) + P(A_2) + \dots + P(A_n).$$

Misol. Yashikda 30 ta shar bor, ulardan 10 tasi qizil, 5 tasi ko‘k va 15 tasi oq. Rangli shar chiqish ehtimolini toping.

Yechish. Rangli shar chiqishi yo qizil shar, yoki ko‘k shar chiqishini bildiradi.

Qizil shar chiqish (A hodisa) ehtimoli.

$$P(A) = \frac{10}{30} = \frac{1}{3}.$$

Ko‘k shar chiqish (B hodisa) ehtimoli:

$$P(B) = \frac{5}{30} = \frac{1}{6}.$$

A va B hodisalar birgalikda emas (bir rangli shar chiqishi boshqa rangli shar chiqishini yo‘qqa chiqaradi), shuning uchun qo‘shish teoremasini qo‘llash mumkin.

$$P(A+B) = P(A) + P(B) = \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{6} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Misol. Birinchi idishda birinchi sortli detallar 30% ni, ikkinchi idishda birinchi sortli detallar 40% ni tashkil etadi. Har bir idishdan bittadan tavakkaliga detallar olinadi. Olingan ikkala detalning ham birinchi sortli bo‘lish ehtimoli topilsin.

Yechish. Masalani yechish uchun masala shartiga e‘tibor qaratamiz.

$P(A)$ ni topish uchun birinchi idishdan olingan detal birinchi sortli bo‘lish ehtimolini topishimiz zarur. Buning uchun:

$$P(A) = \frac{m}{n} = \frac{30\%}{100\%} = 0.3$$

Ikkinchi idishdan olingan detal birinchi sortli bo‘lish ehtimolini topish uchun:

$$P(A) = \frac{m}{n} = \frac{40\%}{100\%} = 0.4$$

Endi umumiy ikkala idishdan olingan ikkala detal ham birinchi sortli chiqish ehtimoli quyidagiga teng ekanligini topamiz:

$$P(A \cdot B) = P(A) \cdot P(B) = 0.3 \cdot 0.4 = 0.12$$

Demak, ikkala idishdan olingan detallar ikkala detal ham birinchi sortli chiqish ehtimoli 0.12 ga teng ekan.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati:

1. Claudio Canute, Anita Tabacco. Mathematical Analysis I,II. Springer-Verlag Italia, Milan
2. X.K.Abduraxmanova, A.A.Abduraxmanov, Z.A.Nalibayeva, I.E.Tursunov, Ehtimollar nazariyasi va matematik statistika bo‘yicha masalalar to‘plami va yechimlari bo‘yicha o‘quv qo‘llanma. T 2021
3. A.Tojiboyev, A.Mamatov “Oddiy differensial tenglamalar” 2009
4. Abdurakhmanova Kh.K., Nalibayeva Z.A.,Roziqov G.A.,Davranova M.Sh., “Applying The Theory Of Differential Equations In Economics” Eurasian Journal of Physics,Chemistry and Mathematics Volume 27 February 2024.
5. X.K.Абдурахманова, И.Турсунов “Современные методы обучения высшей математике студентов технологических вузов” Научный вестник Ташкентского государственного педагогического университета, №1, 2021 г., стр. 101-105.